

Table S1: Differentially expressed genes in FVB-Ala92-Dio2 iBAT as compared to FVB-Thr92-Dio2 iBAT.

Gene ID	P-value (Ala vs Thr)	FDR step up (Ala vs Thr)	Ratio (Ala vs Thr)	Fold change (Ala vs Thr)	LSMean(Ala) (Ala vs Thr)	LSMean(Thr) (Ala vs Thr)
Gdpd3	0.000	0.449	5.94E+01	59.40	7.55E+01	1.27E+00
Rps13-ps1	0.001	0.769	3.35E+01	33.48	9.92E+01	2.96E+00
Kcnk2	0.038	1.000	1.42E+01	14.16	6.91E+00	4.88E-01
Xlr4b	0.028	1.000	1.09E+01	10.88	4.71E+00	4.33E-01
Plekha7	0.000	0.660	9.20E+00	9.20	7.85E+00	8.54E-01
Aqp11	0.017	1.000	6.78E+00	6.78	1.89E+01	2.79E+00
Gm9967	0.001	0.802	6.34E+00	6.34	6.34E+00	9.99E-01
Atp1a3	0.026	1.000	5.66E+00	5.66	4.22E+00	7.45E-01
Metap1d	0.001	0.802	5.22E+00	5.22	4.92E+01	9.42E+00
Sgo2a	0.024	1.000	4.97E+00	4.97	5.87E+00	1.18E+00
Gm4631	0.040	1.000	4.68E+00	4.68	1.25E+01	2.67E+00
Npl	0.031	1.000	4.53E+00	4.53	4.24E+00	9.36E-01
Gm12222	0.001	0.769	4.40E+00	4.40	6.79E+00	1.54E+00
Hif3a	0.005	1.000	4.05E+00	4.05	2.74E+00	6.77E-01
5930430L01Rik	0.014	1.000	4.02E+00	4.02	1.43E+01	3.55E+00
Sycp3	0.031	1.000	3.87E+00	3.87	8.00E+00	2.07E+00
Gm14399	0.048	1.000	3.86E+00	3.86	4.84E+00	1.25E+00
Olfml1	0.004	1.000	3.85E+00	3.85	3.08E+00	7.99E-01
Gm21596	0.012	1.000	3.73E+00	3.73	5.38E+00	1.44E+00
Orai2	0.041	1.000	3.66E+00	3.66	3.10E+00	8.45E-01
Serpine1	0.021	1.000	3.41E+00	3.41	1.13E+01	3.30E+00
Snhg16	0.005	1.000	3.33E+00	3.33	8.59E+00	2.58E+00
Thbs1	0.028	1.000	3.24E+00	3.24	3.49E+01	1.08E+01
Mmp3	0.049	1.000	3.21E+00	3.21	3.77E+00	1.17E+00
Hoga1	0.024	1.000	3.18E+00	3.18	1.99E+00	6.26E-01
Fst	0.006	1.000	2.99E+00	2.99	4.10E+01	1.37E+01
Lacc1	0.032	1.000	2.98E+00	2.98	5.33E+00	1.79E+00
Anxa1	0.010	1.000	2.83E+00	2.83	4.29E+01	1.52E+01
Eif3j1	0.047	1.000	2.78E+00	2.78	3.79E+01	1.36E+01
Dhrs9	0.027	1.000	2.69E+00	2.69	1.32E+01	4.91E+00
Ifi205	0.030	1.000	2.65E+00	2.65	2.08E+01	7.86E+00
Gm7336	0.013	1.000	2.64E+00	2.64	1.44E+02	5.46E+01
Cela1	0.004	1.000	2.62E+00	2.62	2.47E+00	9.43E-01
Slc25a10	0.048	1.000	2.60E+00	2.60	1.70E+01	6.53E+00
H2-M9	0.008	1.000	2.57E+00	2.57	3.54E+00	1.38E+00
Tmem265	0.047	1.000	2.54E+00	2.54	1.97E+00	7.77E-01
Tent5a	0.002	0.860	2.48E+00	2.48	3.01E+01	1.21E+01
Trabd2b	0.039	1.000	2.45E+00	2.45	6.39E+00	2.61E+00
Gabre	0.048	1.000	2.31E+00	2.31	2.46E+00	1.07E+00
Tlcd2	0.016	1.000	2.29E+00	2.29	3.92E+00	1.71E+00

Emilin2	0.028	1.000	2.27E+00	2.27	9.34E+00	4.11E+00
1700018L02Rik	0.050	1.000	2.26E+00	2.26	2.62E+00	1.16E+00
Gm21811	0.026	1.000	2.24E+00	2.24	4.78E+00	2.13E+00
Ciart	0.038	1.000	2.20E+00	2.20	1.61E+01	7.32E+00
Gm14440	0.030	1.000	2.20E+00	2.20	8.49E+00	3.86E+00
Gm43080	0.003	0.944	2.19E+00	2.19	1.60E+00	7.29E-01
Gm7367	0.010	1.000	2.18E+00	2.18	2.91E+00	1.33E+00
Ptges	0.036	1.000	2.16E+00	2.16	7.85E+00	3.63E+00
Odf3l1	0.049	1.000	2.09E+00	2.09	7.69E+00	3.68E+00
Cp	0.002	0.860	2.07E+00	2.07	4.16E+01	2.01E+01
Gm15408	0.028	1.000	2.04E+00	2.04	2.39E+00	1.17E+00
Gm8130	0.042	1.000	2.03E+00	2.03	9.59E+00	4.73E+00
Rel	0.041	1.000	2.02E+00	2.02	1.50E+01	7.43E+00
Net1	0.037	1.000	2.01E+00	2.01	8.06E+01	4.00E+01
Mical2	0.018	1.000	2.00E+00	2.00	4.35E+01	2.18E+01
Resf1	0.027	1.000	1.98E+00	1.98	5.17E+01	2.61E+01
Hspb8	0.028	1.000	1.97E+00	1.97	1.13E+02	5.72E+01
Btg3	0.000	0.769	1.97E+00	1.97	1.23E+01	6.23E+00
Rpl39l	0.049	1.000	1.97E+00	1.97	1.65E+00	8.40E-01
lfrd1	0.019	1.000	1.94E+00	1.94	8.08E+01	4.16E+01
Cited2	0.038	1.000	1.92E+00	1.92	2.17E+01	1.13E+01
Mroh7	0.032	1.000	1.92E+00	1.92	3.08E+00	1.61E+00
Rbm38	0.020	1.000	1.91E+00	1.91	2.31E+01	1.21E+01
Map3k8	0.017	1.000	1.90E+00	1.90	5.78E+00	3.03E+00
Gm6493	0.009	1.000	1.89E+00	1.89	4.21E+00	2.22E+00
Igf1	0.050	1.000	1.89E+00	1.89	2.63E+01	1.39E+01
Herpud1	0.030	1.000	1.87E+00	1.87	1.08E+02	5.77E+01
Cystm1	0.047	1.000	1.86E+00	1.86	4.08E+00	2.20E+00
Gucd1	0.022	1.000	1.83E+00	1.83	1.58E+02	8.61E+01
Gm10602	0.008	1.000	1.83E+00	1.83	6.23E+00	3.41E+00
Tomm6os	0.008	1.000	1.83E+00	1.83	5.12E+00	2.80E+00
Wee1	0.024	1.000	1.82E+00	1.82	7.45E+00	4.10E+00
D330041H03Rik	0.040	1.000	1.80E+00	1.80	1.22E+01	6.76E+00
Mfsd12	0.035	1.000	1.79E+00	1.79	2.60E+01	1.45E+01
Plxnb3	0.023	1.000	1.78E+00	1.78	1.68E+00	9.43E-01
Gm37254	0.002	0.856	1.78E+00	1.78	5.83E+00	3.27E+00
Pcdh7	0.049	1.000	1.76E+00	1.76	3.83E+00	2.18E+00
Fam107a	0.032	1.000	1.76E+00	1.76	9.47E+00	5.38E+00
Cryzl2	0.026	1.000	1.76E+00	1.76	2.56E+01	1.46E+01
Trim68	0.011	1.000	1.76E+00	1.76	1.04E+01	5.92E+00
Ripor2	0.046	1.000	1.75E+00	1.75	6.54E+00	3.72E+00
Nt5e	0.001	0.769	1.75E+00	1.75	3.24E+00	1.84E+00
4930404I05Rik	0.049	1.000	1.75E+00	1.75	4.07E+00	2.33E+00

Lin9	0.015	1.000	1.73E+00	1.73	3.95E+00	2.28E+00
Rpa3	0.020	1.000	1.72E+00	1.72	1.06E+01	6.13E+00
Rnf125	0.043	1.000	1.72E+00	1.72	1.28E+01	7.44E+00
Irf2	0.001	0.802	1.68E+00	1.68	2.72E+01	1.61E+01
Gm14057	0.005	1.000	1.68E+00	1.68	1.49E+00	8.83E-01
Gm43481	0.026	1.000	1.68E+00	1.68	1.49E+00	8.86E-01
Casp3	0.008	1.000	1.67E+00	1.67	1.19E+01	7.14E+00
Wdr70	0.003	0.942	1.67E+00	1.67	1.86E+01	1.11E+01
Gm37123	0.000	0.769	1.67E+00	1.67	2.33E+00	1.40E+00
Zfp759	0.036	1.000	1.66E+00	1.66	4.24E+00	2.55E+00
Rnps1-ps	0.046	1.000	1.66E+00	1.66	1.57E+01	9.47E+00
Ier3	0.010	1.000	1.65E+00	1.65	3.76E+00	2.28E+00
Cdk5rap1	0.044	1.000	1.64E+00	1.64	1.03E+01	6.26E+00
Plekhf1	0.025	1.000	1.62E+00	1.62	2.29E+01	1.41E+01
Vps37a	0.022	1.000	1.61E+00	1.61	9.32E+01	5.78E+01
Ddit3	0.043	1.000	1.61E+00	1.61	3.96E+01	2.47E+01
Mocs2	0.017	1.000	1.61E+00	1.61	1.03E+02	6.43E+01
Zfp975	0.034	1.000	1.59E+00	1.59	7.00E+00	4.40E+00
Matn2	0.003	0.888	1.58E+00	1.58	1.12E+01	7.09E+00
Gm13414	0.005	1.000	1.58E+00	1.58	5.97E+00	3.79E+00
Gm6776	0.023	1.000	1.57E+00	1.57	2.48E+00	1.58E+00
Lrp11	0.007	1.000	1.57E+00	1.57	1.80E+00	1.15E+00
C030015A19Rik	0.040	1.000	1.56E+00	1.56	3.87E+00	2.48E+00
Rif1	0.039	1.000	1.56E+00	1.56	2.00E+01	1.28E+01
Smarce1-ps1	0.015	1.000	1.56E+00	1.56	6.25E+00	4.01E+00
Ccdc17	0.030	1.000	1.54E+00	1.54	2.66E+00	1.72E+00
Lrfn4	0.035	1.000	1.54E+00	1.54	4.15E+00	2.69E+00
Gm9118	0.039	1.000	1.54E+00	1.54	7.59E+00	4.93E+00
Gng5-ps	0.001	0.802	1.54E+00	1.54	2.84E+00	1.85E+00
E2f3	0.039	1.000	1.54E+00	1.54	9.62E+00	6.25E+00
Psma5-ps	0.008	1.000	1.53E+00	1.53	1.42E+01	9.26E+00
Taf1d	0.036	1.000	1.52E+00	1.52	5.49E+01	3.60E+01
Lin54	0.048	1.000	1.52E+00	1.52	8.70E+00	5.72E+00
Clec16a	0.029	1.000	1.51E+00	1.51	4.74E+01	3.13E+01
1700012D14Rik	0.013	1.000	1.51E+00	1.51	2.89E+00	1.91E+00
Atxn7l1	0.011	1.000	1.51E+00	1.51	1.61E+01	1.07E+01
Gm13904	0.022	1.000	1.50E+00	1.50	2.33E+00	1.55E+00
Septin5	0.034	1.000	1.49E+00	1.49	2.90E+00	1.94E+00
Tceanc2	0.002	0.856	1.49E+00	1.49	1.01E+01	6.75E+00
Ppwd1	0.011	1.000	1.49E+00	1.49	1.45E+01	9.76E+00
P4ha1	0.021	1.000	1.48E+00	1.48	1.81E+02	1.22E+02
Cep70	0.035	1.000	1.48E+00	1.48	6.11E+00	4.13E+00
Nipsnap1	0.020	1.000	1.48E+00	1.48	9.08E+00	6.13E+00

Gm14388	0.036	1.000	1.47E+00	1.47	4.61E+00	3.13E+00
Aldh7a1	0.038	1.000	1.47E+00	1.47	3.38E+01	2.30E+01
Gm7334	0.015	1.000	1.47E+00	1.47	1.11E+01	7.56E+00
Hr	0.017	1.000	1.47E+00	1.47	1.66E+01	1.13E+01
Gm50387	0.002	0.860	1.46E+00	1.46	5.51E+00	3.77E+00
Zfp809	0.004	1.000	1.45E+00	1.45	1.35E+01	9.29E+00
Ccdc32	0.018	1.000	1.45E+00	1.45	9.12E+00	6.31E+00
Phf3	0.012	1.000	1.45E+00	1.45	8.22E+01	5.69E+01
E330011O21Rik	0.009	1.000	1.44E+00	1.44	1.10E+01	7.62E+00
Ppargc1b	0.048	1.000	1.44E+00	1.44	6.77E+01	4.70E+01
Mrpl48-ps	0.014	1.000	1.43E+00	1.43	1.87E+01	1.31E+01
Hebp1	0.001	0.802	1.43E+00	1.43	2.50E+01	1.75E+01
Polg2	0.012	1.000	1.43E+00	1.43	5.88E+00	4.12E+00
Gm7407	0.002	0.856	1.42E+00	1.42	5.26E+00	3.70E+00
Kctd18	0.034	1.000	1.42E+00	1.42	1.67E+01	1.18E+01
Peli1	0.027	1.000	1.41E+00	1.41	1.92E+01	1.36E+01
Plekha5	0.003	0.885	1.41E+00	1.41	1.31E+01	9.27E+00
Kmt2c	0.039	1.000	1.41E+00	1.41	7.73E+01	5.48E+01
Psm11	0.007	1.000	1.41E+00	1.41	6.30E+01	4.48E+01
Gm5900	0.041	1.000	1.41E+00	1.41	5.56E+00	3.95E+00
Tex10	0.039	1.000	1.41E+00	1.41	1.23E+01	8.74E+00
Gm12734	0.042	1.000	1.40E+00	1.40	2.10E+00	1.49E+00
Tmcc1	0.027	1.000	1.40E+00	1.40	3.54E+01	2.52E+01
Alkbh1	0.023	1.000	1.40E+00	1.40	1.60E+01	1.15E+01
Zfp869	0.018	1.000	1.40E+00	1.40	3.32E+01	2.38E+01
Gm14048	0.035	1.000	1.39E+00	1.39	1.29E+01	9.28E+00
Tubgcp4	0.033	1.000	1.39E+00	1.39	4.03E+01	2.89E+01
Psm14	0.016	1.000	1.39E+00	1.39	4.91E+01	3.52E+01
Mrpl27-ps	0.028	1.000	1.39E+00	1.39	3.88E+00	2.79E+00
Sqstm1	0.006	1.000	1.39E+00	1.39	2.09E+02	1.51E+02
Pmp22	0.019	1.000	1.38E+00	1.38	6.22E+01	4.52E+01
Nudcd3	0.007	1.000	1.37E+00	1.37	4.95E+01	3.60E+01
Cir1	0.021	1.000	1.37E+00	1.37	1.54E+01	1.13E+01
Fxr1	0.027	1.000	1.37E+00	1.37	1.01E+02	7.36E+01
Rbm33	0.045	1.000	1.37E+00	1.37	6.61E+01	4.84E+01
Ap1b1	0.028	1.000	1.36E+00	1.36	7.05E+01	5.19E+01
Tpmt	0.000	0.769	1.36E+00	1.36	1.28E+01	9.44E+00
Sars2	0.005	1.000	1.36E+00	1.36	1.08E+01	7.94E+00
Abtb1	0.011	1.000	1.35E+00	1.35	2.37E+01	1.75E+01
Nadsyn1	0.007	1.000	1.35E+00	1.35	7.96E+00	5.90E+00
Pds5b	0.020	1.000	1.35E+00	1.35	3.31E+01	2.46E+01
Dock7	0.011	1.000	1.34E+00	1.34	2.23E+01	1.67E+01
Epg5	0.026	1.000	1.34E+00	1.34	2.29E+01	1.71E+01

Fgfr1op	0.046	1.000	1.34E+00	1.34	1.28E+01	9.60E+00
Fam151b	0.015	1.000	1.33E+00	1.33	2.19E+00	1.64E+00
Eif3a	0.044	1.000	1.33E+00	1.33	1.64E+02	1.23E+02
Nf1	0.027	1.000	1.33E+00	1.33	3.97E+01	2.98E+01
Ascc3	0.015	1.000	1.33E+00	1.33	1.53E+01	1.14E+01
Sh3d19	0.035	1.000	1.33E+00	1.33	1.46E+01	1.10E+01
Gm13422	0.030	1.000	1.33E+00	1.33	3.75E+00	2.82E+00
Birc6	0.032	1.000	1.33E+00	1.33	1.12E+02	8.38E+01
Scfd1	0.012	1.000	1.33E+00	1.33	2.44E+01	1.83E+01
Kin	0.036	1.000	1.33E+00	1.33	1.85E+01	1.40E+01
Hnrnp11	0.016	1.000	1.33E+00	1.33	3.34E+01	2.52E+01
Rbm14	0.044	1.000	1.33E+00	1.33	2.81E+01	2.12E+01
Gm14857	0.011	1.000	1.33E+00	1.33	1.45E+00	1.09E+00
Mam1d1	0.023	1.000	1.32E+00	1.32	1.43E+01	1.08E+01
Gpbp1	0.015	1.000	1.32E+00	1.32	6.49E+01	4.92E+01
Cebpg	0.001	0.802	1.32E+00	1.32	1.07E+02	8.11E+01
Acy3	0.036	1.000	1.31E+00	1.31	2.13E+01	1.62E+01
Nup205	0.006	1.000	1.31E+00	1.31	2.62E+01	1.99E+01
Gm43071	0.026	1.000	1.31E+00	1.31	3.23E+00	2.46E+00
Trit1	0.044	1.000	1.31E+00	1.31	2.55E+01	1.95E+01
Psm1	0.046	1.000	1.31E+00	1.31	8.41E+01	6.41E+01
Slc25a19	0.018	1.000	1.31E+00	1.31	3.72E+02	2.84E+02
Tap1	0.009	1.000	1.31E+00	1.31	2.16E+01	1.65E+01
Elmo2	0.014	1.000	1.30E+00	1.30	2.29E+01	1.75E+01
Dpf2	0.004	1.000	1.30E+00	1.30	5.11E+01	3.92E+01
Fbx12	0.019	1.000	1.30E+00	1.30	1.47E+01	1.13E+01
Fam76b	0.045	1.000	1.30E+00	1.30	1.69E+01	1.29E+01
Uhrf1bp1	0.050	1.000	1.30E+00	1.30	3.89E+01	2.99E+01
Edrf1	0.007	1.000	1.30E+00	1.30	1.84E+01	1.41E+01
Cop1	0.030	1.000	1.30E+00	1.30	8.03E+01	6.18E+01
Asf1a	0.018	1.000	1.30E+00	1.30	8.95E+00	6.89E+00
Nckap1	0.050	1.000	1.30E+00	1.30	1.23E+02	9.45E+01
Usp1	0.007	1.000	1.29E+00	1.29	2.14E+01	1.66E+01
Zfp120	0.038	1.000	1.29E+00	1.29	9.67E+00	7.49E+00
Smc3	0.036	1.000	1.29E+00	1.29	3.22E+01	2.50E+01
Gpi1	0.007	1.000	1.29E+00	1.29	6.20E+02	4.81E+02
Washc2	0.000	0.660	1.29E+00	1.29	5.60E+01	4.35E+01
Yap1	0.050	1.000	1.29E+00	1.29	6.35E+01	4.94E+01
Tsc22d2	0.020	1.000	1.28E+00	1.28	2.58E+01	2.01E+01
Orc4	0.017	1.000	1.28E+00	1.28	2.96E+01	2.31E+01
Atad2b	0.007	1.000	1.28E+00	1.28	2.16E+01	1.69E+01
Ints4	0.045	1.000	1.27E+00	1.27	3.29E+01	2.58E+01
Hgs	0.025	1.000	1.27E+00	1.27	3.02E+01	2.37E+01

Rabggtb	0.020	1.000	1.27E+00	1.27	6.06E+01	4.77E+01
Ctr9	0.029	1.000	1.27E+00	1.27	4.01E+01	3.16E+01
Med17	0.039	1.000	1.27E+00	1.27	1.45E+01	1.14E+01
Blmh	0.021	1.000	1.27E+00	1.27	2.19E+01	1.73E+01
Atf5	0.049	1.000	1.27E+00	1.27	1.11E+02	8.74E+01
Tstd2	0.047	1.000	1.27E+00	1.27	2.63E+01	2.08E+01
Mocos	0.048	1.000	1.27E+00	1.27	5.23E+00	4.13E+00
Ndufaf1	0.002	0.876	1.26E+00	1.26	3.70E+01	2.92E+01
Htt	0.011	1.000	1.26E+00	1.26	4.61E+01	3.67E+01
Mapk8	0.005	1.000	1.26E+00	1.26	2.19E+01	1.74E+01
Nmt2	0.027	1.000	1.25E+00	1.25	6.54E+01	5.21E+01
Rnf2	0.042	1.000	1.25E+00	1.25	2.68E+01	2.13E+01
Nat8f1	0.047	1.000	1.25E+00	1.25	2.00E+00	1.59E+00
Cstf1	0.003	0.944	1.25E+00	1.25	2.43E+01	1.94E+01
Ypel5	0.011	1.000	1.25E+00	1.25	5.28E+01	4.22E+01
Phf8	0.030	1.000	1.25E+00	1.25	2.08E+01	1.67E+01
Orc5	0.033	1.000	1.25E+00	1.25	1.55E+01	1.24E+01
Tnks	0.008	1.000	1.25E+00	1.25	4.08E+01	3.27E+01
Mkln1	0.041	1.000	1.25E+00	1.25	7.55E+01	6.06E+01
Cutc	0.015	1.000	1.24E+00	1.24	8.36E+00	6.72E+00
Mllt3	0.001	0.802	1.24E+00	1.24	7.18E+00	5.77E+00
Plaa	0.009	1.000	1.24E+00	1.24	4.33E+01	3.49E+01
Fndc3a	0.001	0.802	1.24E+00	1.24	3.63E+01	2.92E+01
Akap10	0.030	1.000	1.24E+00	1.24	1.96E+01	1.58E+01
Usp3	0.041	1.000	1.24E+00	1.24	1.68E+01	1.36E+01
Fbxo11	0.018	1.000	1.24E+00	1.24	7.04E+01	5.70E+01
Srp19	0.046	1.000	1.23E+00	1.23	2.35E+01	1.91E+01
Gm6997	0.021	1.000	1.23E+00	1.23	3.73E+00	3.02E+00
Tax1bp1	0.049	1.000	1.23E+00	1.23	1.10E+02	8.94E+01
Hspa14	0.037	1.000	1.23E+00	1.23	2.05E+01	1.66E+01
1810013L24Rik	0.012	1.000	1.23E+00	1.23	5.47E+01	4.44E+01
BC005537	0.026	1.000	1.23E+00	1.23	1.73E+02	1.40E+02
Sars	0.031	1.000	1.23E+00	1.23	7.07E+01	5.76E+01
2900097C17Rik	0.045	1.000	1.23E+00	1.23	1.51E+02	1.23E+02
Dcaf7	0.040	1.000	1.23E+00	1.23	3.62E+01	2.95E+01
Ncoa6	0.010	1.000	1.23E+00	1.23	3.50E+01	2.86E+01
Gm6644	0.031	1.000	1.23E+00	1.23	2.33E+01	1.90E+01
Mical3	0.040	1.000	1.22E+00	1.22	7.30E+01	5.97E+01
Gm2541	0.031	1.000	1.22E+00	1.22	2.55E+00	2.09E+00
Bach1	0.037	1.000	1.22E+00	1.22	3.13E+01	2.56E+01
Psme4	0.026	1.000	1.22E+00	1.22	8.52E+01	7.00E+01
Zfp871	0.030	1.000	1.22E+00	1.22	5.08E+01	4.18E+01
Dnm1l	0.041	1.000	1.22E+00	1.22	9.77E+01	8.03E+01

Gm4596	0.033	1.000	1.21E+00	1.21	1.97E+01	1.62E+01
Fubp3	0.043	1.000	1.21E+00	1.21	1.31E+01	1.08E+01
Eif2s3y	0.009	1.000	1.21E+00	1.21	7.35E+01	6.06E+01
Sec31a	0.035	1.000	1.21E+00	1.21	8.69E+01	7.19E+01
Fam214b	0.039	1.000	1.21E+00	1.21	2.72E+01	2.25E+01
Nepro	0.038	1.000	1.21E+00	1.21	9.98E+00	8.28E+00
Rab3gap2	0.027	1.000	1.20E+00	1.20	2.67E+01	2.21E+01
Rsf1	0.026	1.000	1.20E+00	1.20	2.47E+01	2.05E+01
Kantr	0.034	1.000	1.20E+00	1.20	3.98E+00	3.31E+00
Gm20075	0.026	1.000	1.20E+00	1.20	4.77E+01	3.96E+01
Dennd4c	0.019	1.000	1.20E+00	1.20	3.38E+01	2.82E+01
Psmb7	0.016	1.000	1.20E+00	1.20	1.03E+02	8.62E+01
Washc5	0.006	1.000	1.20E+00	1.20	2.67E+01	2.24E+01
Myo19	0.003	0.885	1.19E+00	1.19	1.59E+01	1.33E+01
Dars2	0.047	1.000	1.19E+00	1.19	1.56E+01	1.31E+01
Helz	0.048	1.000	1.19E+00	1.19	2.52E+01	2.11E+01
Psmc6	0.008	1.000	1.19E+00	1.19	8.67E+01	7.27E+01
Ccdc6	0.045	1.000	1.19E+00	1.19	3.34E+01	2.80E+01
Pi4k2a	0.050	1.000	1.19E+00	1.19	3.27E+01	2.75E+01
Prpf40a	0.027	1.000	1.19E+00	1.19	3.69E+01	3.10E+01
Cpsf2	0.011	1.000	1.19E+00	1.19	2.34E+01	1.97E+01
Nktr	0.010	1.000	1.18E+00	1.18	9.34E+01	7.89E+01
Raf1	0.024	1.000	1.18E+00	1.18	8.14E+01	6.88E+01
Plpbp	0.044	1.000	1.18E+00	1.18	6.68E+01	5.66E+01
Sergef	0.013	1.000	1.18E+00	1.18	2.24E+00	1.90E+00
Kat7	0.019	1.000	1.18E+00	1.18	3.57E+01	3.02E+01
Ube2d-ps	0.026	1.000	1.18E+00	1.18	2.25E+01	1.91E+01
Ppard	0.050	1.000	1.17E+00	1.17	2.00E+01	1.71E+01
Srp68	0.024	1.000	1.17E+00	1.17	3.51E+01	3.00E+01
Cnot7	0.031	1.000	1.17E+00	1.17	4.74E+01	4.05E+01
Smim15	0.034	1.000	1.17E+00	1.17	2.29E+01	1.96E+01
Mex3c	0.040	1.000	1.17E+00	1.17	2.35E+01	2.01E+01
N6amt1	0.001	0.802	1.16E+00	1.16	1.42E+01	1.22E+01
Clasp1	0.039	1.000	1.15E+00	1.15	3.20E+01	2.77E+01
Rbbp5	0.013	1.000	1.15E+00	1.15	2.02E+01	1.76E+01
Mdh1	0.011	1.000	1.14E+00	1.14	5.43E+02	4.75E+02
Mtg1	0.045	1.000	1.14E+00	1.14	3.08E+01	2.69E+01
BC031181	0.034	1.000	1.14E+00	1.14	4.69E+01	4.11E+01
Copa	0.040	1.000	1.14E+00	1.14	1.39E+02	1.22E+02
Fbxl5	0.023	1.000	1.14E+00	1.14	3.31E+01	2.91E+01
Zmym2	0.049	1.000	1.13E+00	1.13	2.90E+01	2.56E+01
Mrpl47	0.004	1.000	1.12E+00	1.12	2.63E+01	2.35E+01
Tfg	0.026	1.000	1.12E+00	1.12	5.03E+01	4.50E+01

Nmt1	0.030	1.000	1.11E+00	1.11	8.69E+01	7.80E+01
Slc31a1	0.026	1.000	1.11E+00	1.11	3.00E+01	2.69E+01
Gart	0.007	1.000	1.10E+00	1.10	3.25E+01	2.96E+01
Mrps30	0.006	1.000	1.09E+00	1.09	3.94E+01	3.61E+01
Vcpip1	0.037	1.000	1.08E+00	1.08	2.38E+01	2.20E+01
E2f6	0.015	1.000	9.01E-01	-1.11	2.49E+01	2.77E+01
Cyc1	0.043	1.000	8.96E-01	-1.12	6.50E+02	7.25E+02
Kdelr1	0.039	1.000	8.92E-01	-1.12	5.64E+01	6.32E+01
Uqcrc1	0.030	1.000	8.86E-01	-1.13	1.02E+03	1.16E+03
Tvp23b	0.035	1.000	8.84E-01	-1.13	1.43E+01	1.61E+01
Slc48a1	0.045	1.000	8.83E-01	-1.13	6.89E+01	7.80E+01
Thoc3	0.029	1.000	8.74E-01	-1.14	2.04E+01	2.33E+01
Ubxn6	0.040	1.000	8.72E-01	-1.15	4.49E+01	5.15E+01
Marchf2	0.030	1.000	8.71E-01	-1.15	7.69E+01	8.83E+01
Pip4k2c	0.029	1.000	8.67E-01	-1.15	3.00E+01	3.46E+01
Rnf138	0.004	1.000	8.59E-01	-1.16	1.43E+01	1.67E+01
Gm10925	0.007	1.000	8.56E-01	-1.17	2.15E+04	2.51E+04
mt-Atp6	0.006	1.000	8.52E-01	-1.17	2.17E+04	2.54E+04
Tmem245	0.048	1.000	8.50E-01	-1.18	7.56E+01	8.89E+01
mt-Cytb	0.027	1.000	8.45E-01	-1.18	3.64E+04	4.31E+04
Lrrc56	0.012	1.000	8.44E-01	-1.18	5.21E+00	6.17E+00
Suclg1	0.005	1.000	8.39E-01	-1.19	6.99E+02	8.33E+02
Hagh	0.021	1.000	8.38E-01	-1.19	6.01E+01	7.17E+01
Kcnn1	0.033	1.000	8.30E-01	-1.20	6.56E+00	7.91E+00
Mapkapk2	0.033	1.000	8.28E-01	-1.21	1.40E+02	1.69E+02
BC025920	0.034	1.000	8.28E-01	-1.21	3.91E+00	4.72E+00
Msrp3	0.043	1.000	8.26E-01	-1.21	4.27E+01	5.18E+01
Pigm	0.044	1.000	8.26E-01	-1.21	2.20E+01	2.67E+01
Plekhb2	0.038	1.000	8.24E-01	-1.21	2.87E+01	3.48E+01
Rcan3	0.006	1.000	8.19E-01	-1.22	8.94E+00	1.09E+01
Emc10	0.048	1.000	8.19E-01	-1.22	4.61E+01	5.63E+01
Wdr47	0.027	1.000	8.18E-01	-1.22	7.10E+00	8.68E+00
Hspa13	0.041	1.000	8.18E-01	-1.22	1.50E+01	1.83E+01
Chml	0.006	1.000	8.15E-01	-1.23	6.17E+00	7.58E+00
Swsap1	0.015	1.000	8.14E-01	-1.23	6.94E+00	8.52E+00
Zfp931	0.039	1.000	8.13E-01	-1.23	1.37E+01	1.68E+01
Popdc2	0.050	1.000	8.09E-01	-1.24	1.06E+01	1.31E+01
Gm28661	0.048	1.000	8.09E-01	-1.24	1.64E+04	2.03E+04
mt-Co2	0.048	1.000	8.08E-01	-1.24	1.64E+04	2.03E+04
Sdr39u1	0.002	0.860	8.06E-01	-1.24	4.56E+01	5.66E+01
Glo1	0.004	1.000	8.04E-01	-1.24	3.87E+01	4.81E+01
Bcat2	0.034	1.000	8.04E-01	-1.24	7.49E+01	9.31E+01
Zfp523	0.002	0.856	8.03E-01	-1.25	1.03E+01	1.28E+01

Tmem246	0.018	1.000	8.01E-01	-1.25	1.81E+01	2.26E+01
Fgf11	0.029	1.000	7.91E-01	-1.26	8.88E+00	1.12E+01
Gm13341	0.019	1.000	7.89E-01	-1.27	7.14E+00	9.06E+00
Tmem177	0.015	1.000	7.81E-01	-1.28	9.62E+00	1.23E+01
Tm7sf3	0.008	1.000	7.78E-01	-1.28	1.19E+01	1.52E+01
Pigw	0.022	1.000	7.78E-01	-1.29	4.37E+00	5.61E+00
Alg1	0.041	1.000	7.76E-01	-1.29	1.31E+01	1.69E+01
Dynll2	0.045	1.000	7.74E-01	-1.29	9.08E+01	1.17E+02
Gnl3l	0.028	1.000	7.71E-01	-1.30	1.12E+01	1.45E+01
mt-Nd1	0.040	1.000	7.70E-01	-1.30	1.37E+04	1.79E+04
5730409E04Rik	0.011	1.000	7.63E-01	-1.31	6.97E+00	9.13E+00
Cep19	0.009	1.000	7.62E-01	-1.31	5.36E+00	7.04E+00
Bbs1	0.039	1.000	7.59E-01	-1.32	2.70E+00	3.55E+00
Acp1	0.002	0.860	7.54E-01	-1.33	2.96E+01	3.93E+01
Kidins220	0.027	1.000	7.52E-01	-1.33	6.50E+01	8.65E+01
Rdh10	0.040	1.000	7.51E-01	-1.33	7.76E+00	1.03E+01
4933431E20Rik	0.006	1.000	7.46E-01	-1.34	3.12E+00	4.19E+00
Slc16a1	0.008	1.000	7.44E-01	-1.34	2.20E+02	2.96E+02
Gm37691	0.032	1.000	7.39E-01	-1.35	7.42E+00	1.00E+01
Klhl12	0.019	1.000	7.38E-01	-1.35	1.31E+01	1.77E+01
Oxct1	0.014	1.000	7.32E-01	-1.37	2.28E+02	3.12E+02
Dlg3	0.029	1.000	7.31E-01	-1.37	5.52E+00	7.54E+00
Kcnk3	0.009	1.000	7.16E-01	-1.40	2.46E+02	3.44E+02
Tbc1d24	0.011	1.000	7.15E-01	-1.40	1.39E+01	1.95E+01
Mpp6	0.040	1.000	7.10E-01	-1.41	1.59E+01	2.24E+01
Ism1	0.028	1.000	7.09E-01	-1.41	2.49E+00	3.51E+00
Tmem94	0.003	0.885	7.02E-01	-1.42	5.94E+01	8.46E+01
Kdsr	0.020	1.000	7.00E-01	-1.43	2.27E+01	3.25E+01
Dnal1	0.025	1.000	6.98E-01	-1.43	4.61E+00	6.60E+00
Rassf3	0.039	1.000	6.97E-01	-1.43	3.21E+01	4.60E+01
4933440N22Rik	0.036	1.000	6.95E-01	-1.44	9.24E-01	1.33E+00
Tmem64	0.010	1.000	6.94E-01	-1.44	2.65E+01	3.81E+01
Pbld2	0.047	1.000	6.91E-01	-1.45	9.69E-01	1.40E+00
Ro60	0.008	1.000	6.89E-01	-1.45	9.97E+00	1.45E+01
Gm47595	0.025	1.000	6.76E-01	-1.48	9.94E-01	1.47E+00
Gm28438	0.021	1.000	6.72E-01	-1.49	1.29E+03	1.91E+03
Hexim2	0.003	0.944	6.72E-01	-1.49	1.58E+00	2.35E+00
Rnf217	0.010	1.000	6.71E-01	-1.49	6.12E+00	9.12E+00
Eif3j2	0.001	0.802	6.65E-01	-1.50	4.01E+01	6.03E+01
Dnajc27	0.009	1.000	6.59E-01	-1.52	4.75E+00	7.21E+00
Cadm4	0.010	1.000	6.58E-01	-1.52	2.12E+00	3.23E+00
Slc2a12	0.023	1.000	6.51E-01	-1.54	1.38E+00	2.12E+00
Zfp354c	0.014	1.000	6.51E-01	-1.54	2.06E+00	3.16E+00

AA986860	0.032	1.000	6.49E-01	-1.54	2.56E+00	3.94E+00
Gm10032	0.015	1.000	6.45E-01	-1.55	2.88E+01	4.46E+01
Pars2	0.022	1.000	6.40E-01	-1.56	3.57E+00	5.58E+00
Vstm4	0.042	1.000	6.38E-01	-1.57	3.69E+00	5.79E+00
Efs	0.038	1.000	6.35E-01	-1.58	5.91E+00	9.30E+00
Nim1k	0.033	1.000	6.34E-01	-1.58	2.58E+00	4.07E+00
Tshz2	0.030	1.000	6.33E-01	-1.58	2.21E+01	3.49E+01
Magee1	0.030	1.000	6.33E-01	-1.58	2.37E+00	3.74E+00
Slx1b	0.047	1.000	6.32E-01	-1.58	7.48E+00	1.18E+01
Ccdc126	0.004	1.000	6.31E-01	-1.59	2.92E+00	4.64E+00
Mcc	0.025	1.000	6.21E-01	-1.61	2.97E+01	4.78E+01
Gm50240	0.026	1.000	6.20E-01	-1.61	1.73E+00	2.79E+00
Igf2	0.033	1.000	6.16E-01	-1.62	1.05E+01	1.71E+01
mt-Nd3	0.015	1.000	6.12E-01	-1.63	1.11E+03	1.81E+03
Ahr	0.037	1.000	6.11E-01	-1.64	1.24E+01	2.02E+01
4930518I15Rik	0.000	0.769	6.10E-01	-1.64	1.06E+00	1.74E+00
Trmt9b	0.045	1.000	6.09E-01	-1.64	3.83E+00	6.29E+00
Tmem266	0.023	1.000	6.08E-01	-1.65	1.37E+00	2.25E+00
Tdg-ps2	0.017	1.000	6.06E-01	-1.65	2.15E+00	3.54E+00
Gde1	0.050	1.000	5.97E-01	-1.68	5.45E+01	9.13E+01
Rbfa	0.022	1.000	5.88E-01	-1.70	2.16E+01	3.68E+01
Kctd7	0.050	1.000	5.85E-01	-1.71	1.86E+00	3.18E+00
Mmd2	0.038	1.000	5.82E-01	-1.72	7.41E+00	1.27E+01
Npr3	0.032	1.000	5.66E-01	-1.77	7.00E+01	1.24E+02
Tpd52l1	0.017	1.000	5.64E-01	-1.77	2.03E+00	3.60E+00
Prom1	0.036	1.000	5.60E-01	-1.79	2.20E+00	3.93E+00
Lncbate1	0.028	1.000	5.42E-01	-1.84	1.00E+01	1.85E+01
4933406C10Rik	0.029	1.000	5.41E-01	-1.85	1.38E+00	2.56E+00
Gm16124	0.044	1.000	5.30E-01	-1.89	2.24E+00	4.22E+00
Car14	0.027	1.000	5.29E-01	-1.89	9.03E+00	1.71E+01
Rsph3b	0.005	1.000	5.28E-01	-1.89	3.54E+01	6.70E+01
Marchf9	0.030	1.000	5.15E-01	-1.94	8.29E-01	1.61E+00
St3gal5	0.050	1.000	5.12E-01	-1.95	1.77E+01	3.46E+01
1700052K11Rik	0.009	1.000	5.10E-01	-1.96	3.53E+00	6.93E+00
Pcdhga4	0.041	1.000	5.07E-01	-1.97	8.49E-01	1.67E+00
Hic1	0.037	1.000	5.05E-01	-1.98	6.46E+00	1.28E+01
Abca5	0.042	1.000	5.02E-01	-1.99	6.36E+00	1.27E+01
Lzts3	0.014	1.000	4.89E-01	-2.05	2.26E+00	4.62E+00
Il17re	0.008	1.000	4.88E-01	-2.05	4.54E+00	9.30E+00
Paox	0.010	1.000	4.87E-01	-2.06	6.76E+00	1.39E+01
Sord	0.010	1.000	4.83E-01	-2.07	4.32E+01	8.94E+01
Gm9493	0.046	1.000	4.81E-01	-2.08	1.55E+01	3.22E+01
Osbp2	0.027	1.000	4.79E-01	-2.09	1.31E+00	2.75E+00

Gm39244	0.002	0.860	4.66E-01	-2.15	8.91E-01	1.91E+00
Lipt2	0.005	1.000	4.62E-01	-2.16	2.03E+00	4.39E+00
Kcnj8	0.032	1.000	4.62E-01	-2.16	9.93E+00	2.15E+01
Amotl2	0.049	1.000	4.50E-01	-2.22	3.28E+01	7.30E+01
E430018J23Rik	0.023	1.000	4.48E-01	-2.23	1.91E+00	4.26E+00
Wnt11	0.042	1.000	4.46E-01	-2.24	2.13E+00	4.77E+00
Entpd4	0.030	1.000	4.36E-01	-2.29	6.32E+01	1.45E+02
Gm9870	0.024	1.000	4.34E-01	-2.30	6.91E-01	1.59E+00
Rgs6	0.033	1.000	4.29E-01	-2.33	1.29E+00	3.01E+00
Heyl	0.023	1.000	4.19E-01	-2.39	9.96E+00	2.38E+01
Acot6	0.043	1.000	3.94E-01	-2.54	1.62E+00	4.12E+00
Entpd4b	0.022	1.000	3.85E-01	-2.60	5.44E+01	1.42E+02
Gabra2	0.038	1.000	3.84E-01	-2.60	1.04E+00	2.70E+00
Hbb-bt	0.025	1.000	3.81E-01	-2.62	1.46E+01	3.82E+01
Angptl1	0.008	1.000	3.71E-01	-2.70	2.36E+00	6.37E+00
Gm21955	0.018	1.000	3.63E-01	-2.75	1.67E+00	4.59E+00
Gm11769	0.011	1.000	3.61E-01	-2.77	7.06E-01	1.96E+00
Cth	0.001	0.802	3.51E-01	-2.85	9.68E-01	2.76E+00
Gmpr	0.046	1.000	3.49E-01	-2.86	6.71E+01	1.92E+02
Hspa1l	0.013	1.000	3.35E-01	-2.99	6.97E-01	2.08E+00
BC067074	0.031	1.000	3.18E-01	-3.15	1.56E+00	4.92E+00
Tmem254c	0.046	1.000	3.11E-01	-3.22	1.87E+00	6.01E+00
Gm4875	0.007	1.000	3.06E-01	-3.26	9.78E-01	3.19E+00
Cldn1	0.018	1.000	2.92E-01	-3.43	8.54E-01	2.93E+00
Rab4a	0.003	0.962	2.88E-01	-3.47	1.37E+00	4.77E+00
Trim34a	0.028	1.000	2.86E-01	-3.50	2.08E+00	7.26E+00
Mid1	0.006	1.000	2.67E-01	-3.75	8.94E+00	3.35E+01
Rps13	0.008	1.000	2.23E-01	-4.49	5.02E+00	2.26E+01
G530011O06Rik	0.002	0.856	1.96E-01	-5.10	5.12E-01	2.61E+00
Gpx8	0.013	1.000	1.16E-01	-8.58	1.08E+01	9.25E+01
Lgr6	0.009	1.000	1.15E-01	-8.72	1.82E+01	1.59E+02
Psmc3ip	0.001	0.802	9.44E-02	-10.59	1.34E+00	1.42E+01
Gvin1	0.002	0.860	7.76E-02	-12.88	8.20E+00	1.06E+02
Gchfr	0.001	0.802	2.95E-02	-33.88	4.55E-01	1.54E+01
Rps13-ps2	0.011	1.000	6.93E-03	-144.38	4.62E-01	6.66E+01